

DDQ (2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-*p*-benzoquinone) as a chromogenic reagent for the determination of clindamycin hydrochloride, clomiphene citrate and mefloquine hydrochloride

G. P. V. Mallikarjuna Rao^a, P. Aruna Devi^a, K. M. M. Krishna Prasad^a and C. S. P. Sastry^{b*}

^aDepartment of Physical, Nuclear and Chemical Oceanography, ^bDepartment of Organic Chemistry, Foods, Drugs & Water, School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, India

E-mail : orgchem@satyasaionline.net.in Fax : 91-0891-755574

Manuscript received 21 December 2001, accepted 12 June 2002

A spectrophotometric method for the estimation of the drugs clindamycin hydrochloride, clomiphene citrate and mefloquine hydrochloride is described. This method is based on coloured radical anion formation (λ_{\max} 460 nm) when the drug (*n*-electron donor) solutions are treated with DDQ (π -acceptor) reagent.

Clindamycin hydrochloride (CM)^{1,2} (antibacterial), clomiphene citrate (CP)¹⁻³ (gonad stimulate) and mefloquine hydrochloride (MQ)^{1,4} (antimalarial) are widely used as drugs. There are several spectrophotometric (visible region) methods for the estimation of these drugs involving various reagents⁵. We describe here a spectrophotometric method for the estimation of these drugs (*n*-electron donors) based on the formation of colored radical anion (λ_{\max} 460 nm for CM, CP or MQ) when the drug solutions are treated with 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-*p*-benzoquinone (DDQ)⁶ (π -acceptor) reagent.

Results and Discussion

Among the quinone derivatives such as chloranil, chloranilic acid, DDQ was found to be good due to higher sensitivity. Maximum absorbance was observed when 2.0 ml of 0.1% DDQ solution was used. Among the solvents tried such as benzene, carbon tetrachloride, 1,4-dioxane, dichloromethane and chloroform, the latter was found best to get high yields of radical anion of maximum intensity. A 30 min (CM or MQ) or 15 min (CP) keeping time was found necessary for attaining maximum intensity of colored radical anion.

The effects of various substances that often accompany in various pharmaceutical formulation were studied. To an aliquot (containing 1000 μg of CM, 500 μg of CP or 400 μg of MQ) of the drug, different amounts of various ingredients and additives were added until the solution showed same absorbance (± 0.01) as that of pure drug (CM, CP or MQ) solution under experimental conditions. The commonly used ingredients and additives in the preparation

of formulation such as talc (upto 200-fold excess, w/v), starch (150-fold), boric acid (150-fold), stearic acid (70-fold), magnesium stearate (50-fold), kaolin (30-fold), sodium lauryl sulfate (10-fold) and gelatin (10-fold) did not interfere with the assay of CM, CP or MQ by proposed method.

The optical characteristics such as Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), molar extinction coefficient ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) and Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001$ absorbance unit) were found to be 20–150, 1.113×10^3 , 0.381 for CM; 10–70, 4.617×10^3 , 0.259 for CP and 8–60, 2.955×10^3 , 0.140 for MQ, respectively. The slope, intercept and correlation coefficient obtained by linear least-squares treatment were found to be 2.618×10^{-3} , 4.0×10^{-4} , 0.9999 for CM; 9.665×10^{-3} , -9.525×10^{-2} , 0.9999 for CP and 7.122×10^{-3} , 5.33×10^{-4} , 0.9999 for MQ, respectively. The precision and accuracy of the method was tested by estimating six replicate samples of the drugs within Beer's law limits. The percent relative standard deviation and percentage range of error (95% confidence limit) were found to be 0.623, 0.654 for CM; 0.314, 0.323 for CP and 0.412, 0.433 for MQ, respectively.

Commercially available pharmaceutical preparations were successfully analyzed by the proposed method. The values obtained by the proposed and reference methods for pharmaceutical preparations were compared statistically by the *t*- and *F*-tests⁷ and found not to differ significantly. As an additional demonstration of accuracy, recovery experiments were performed by adding fixed amount of the drug to the preanalyzed formations. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table I. Analysis of pharmaceutical formulations

Drug / formulations ^d	Labelled amount mg	Amount found (mg) ^b		% Recovery proposed method ^c
		Proposed method	Reference method CM ^d , CP ^e , MQ ^f	
CM		148.35 ± 0.57		
Capsules-I	150	$F=1.53$ $t=1.64$	149.73 ± 0.46	98.89 ± 0.38
Capsules-II	150	148.21 ± 0.87 $F=1.52$ $t=2.1$	148.89 ± 1.09	99.49 ± 0.58
Capsules-III	150	147.98 ± 1.13 $F=3.93$ $t=2.0$	149.42 ± 0.57	98.81 ± 0.58
Capsules-IV	150	148.66 ± 0.86 $F=1.75$ $t=1.52$	149.62 ± 0.65	99.10 ± 0.57
CP		50.02 ± 0.43		
Tablets-I	50	$F=1.31$ $t=0.53$	49.81 ± 0.32	100.04 ± 0.83
Tablets-II	50	50.02 ± 0.21 $F=3.06$ $t=0.61$	50.13 ± 0.12	100.05 ± 0.43
Tablets-III	25	24.97 ± 0.25 $F=2.05$ $t=1.5$	25.05 ± 0.18	99.91 ± 1.0
Tablets-IV	25	25.11 ± 0.11 $F=1.09$ $t=0.06$	25.12 ± 0.115	100.21 ± 0.70
MQ		250.58 ± 1.0		
Tablets-I	250	$F=1.27$ $t=1.02$	250.97 ± 0.89	100.23 ± 0.39
Tablets-II	250	249.41 ± 1.01 $F=2.34$ $t=1.86$	250.38 ± 0.66	99.76 ± 0.40
Tablets-III	250	249.02 ± 0.89 $F=1.28$ $t=1.51$	250.58 ± 1.01	99.61 ± 0.35
Tablets-IV	250	249.12 ± 0.87 $F=1.04$ $t=1.83$	250.17 ± 0.89	99.64 ± 0.35

^aFour types of capsules (CM) and tablets (CP or MQ) from four different pharmaceutical companies.

^bAverage ± standard deviation of six determinations; t - and F -test values refer to comparison of the proposed methods with the reference method. Theoretical values at 95% confidence limits, $t=2.57$, $F=5.05$.

^cRecovery of 10 mg added to the pharmaceutical formulations (average of 3 determinations).

^dDeveloped in laboratory for CM in 0.1 N H₂SO₄ (λ_{\max} 218 nm). ^eRefs. 1,2. ^fRef. 4.

Experimental

A Milton Roy Spectronic 1201 and Systronics 106 spectrophotometers with 1 cm matched quartz cells were used.

All reagents and chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used. A 0.1% (w/v) of DDQ solution in chloroform was prepared.

CM, CP or MQ sample (50 mg) was treated with 0.1 N NaOH solution (10 ml). The mixture was extracted with chloroform (3 × 15 ml). The total chloroform extract was filtered, dried with anhyd. sodium sulfate (2 g) and made up to 50 ml with chloroform to obtain 1 mg / ml standard solutions.

Capsule (CM) or tablet (CP or MQ) powder equivalent to 50 mg of the drug (CM, CP or MQ) was taken and the sample solution was prepared in the same manner as mentioned in the standard drug solution preparation.

Procedure : To aliquot of standard drug solution (CM : 250–1500 µg; CP : 200–700 µg; MQ : 100–600 µg) was added DDQ solution (2.0 ml) and set aside (30 min for CM or MQ and 15 min for CP). The volume was then made upto 10 ml (CM, CP or MQ) with chloroform and read at 460 nm (CM, CP or MQ) against reagent blank during the stable period (immediate to 45 min). The amount of drug present (CM, CP or MQ) was computed from the appropriate calibration curve.

References

1. "British Pharmacopoeia", HMSO, London, 1999.
2. "United States Pharmacopoeia", 24th. ed., USP Convention, Rockville, 2000.
3. "Indian Pharmacopoeia". Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, New Delhi, 1996.
4. "Analytical Profiles of Drug Substances", Academic, New York, 1985, Vol. 14.
5. El-Yazbi, A. Fawzyo and Black M. Salah, *Analyst*, 1993, **118**, 577; M. F. Attia, *J. Annal. Chem.*, 1994, **3**, 173; A. S. Amin, *Analysis*, 1995, **23**, 415; I. I. Hewala, *Anal. Lett.*, 1993, **26**, 625; A. Assamoi, M. Hamom and M. Chaigneau, *Talanta*, 1987, **32**, 1015; S. A. Adelusi and A. O. Onyekwali, *Pak. J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1996, **39**, 22.
6. K. Kelani and L. I. Bebavy, *Anal. Lett.*, 1997, **30**, 1843; M. E. A. Hamid and M. Alidel-Salam, *Talanta*, 1995, **32**, 1002; A. S. Issa and M. S. Mahrous, *Talanta*, 1987, **34**, 670.
7. D. L. Massart, B. G. M. Vandeginste, S. N. Demung, Y. Michotte and I. Kafufman, "Chemometrics", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1988.